

COMPOSITE AIRCRAFT FUSELAGE STRUCTURE BLUNT IMPACT DAMAGE PREDICTION METHODOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Due to their high performance and weight efficiency, carbon fiber composites are increasingly being used in aircraft primary structure applications. Exposed composite structures (e.g., fuselage lower body) are susceptible to accidental impacts by ground service equipment (GSE). Due to their very high mass (10^3 to 10^4 kg range) GSE impact can involve high energy (10^3 J) and thus can induce significant internal damage. Furthermore, due to the large contact area of GSE rubber-faced bumpers, extensive internal delamination and fiber failure can be created without leaving exterior-visible signs that any damage has occurred. The objectives of the research described herein is to establish a modeling methodology involving detailed simulation capability that is validated via small-scale element-level tests, and then applying these capabilities to accurately predict full-scale structural behavior without adjustment (e.g., tuning) of modeling input parameters.

1 INTRODUCTION

Damage to commercial aircraft from ground service equipment (GSE) is the largest source of major damage [1]. GSE includes belt and cargo loaders, fuel and food service trucks, and general equipment that operates in near proximity to the aircraft. These often have rubber/elastomeric bumpers (called spacers) mounted to protruding surfaces and particularly at locations that come very close to, or even in direct contact with, the aircraft outer surface. GSE movement is typically human-controlled (e.g., pedals to move, stop), and thus GSE does make accidental contact with aircraft. While not all contact events are damaging, high energy impact-contact can occur even at low velocities (less than 2 km/hr) due to the high mass typical of some GSE (over 10,000 kg for large cargo loaders). On metal-skinned aircraft, severe impact from GSE would be visually observable due to the subsequent dent imparted to the skin. For composite skins, which can have much higher strength than the aluminum alloys, the visibility of any residual dents from GSE impact can be significantly smaller or even non-existent.

The bluntness of an impactor has a significant effect on the creation of local damage [2, 3]. The impact energy and peak force at which initial delamination damage forms was found to be much higher for increasing impactor tip radius [3]. Larger radius tips produce a lower peak strain and more widespread strain distribution (spatially), and impacts where a rubber pad was placed between the impactor and composite panel target were observed to significantly reduce the peak strain (local to impact site) even further. Thus, since a structure impacted with a larger-radius blunt impactor involves considerably more force to initiate local damage, failures occurring at locations further away, e.g., at boundaries and joint locations, can possibly occur under blunt impact loading, even without the formation of local (at impact site) damage [4].

Impact damage prediction in composites, while still an ongoing research topic, is a moderately-mature analysis within the Finite Element (FE) framework, used by specialized R&D groups (not routine for general engineering). Bird impact and fan blade-out simulations have been used by engine companies since 1990s. More recent advances, since the mid 2000s, allowing for nodal separation due to fracture processes have permitted prediction of delamination via virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) and cohesive zone approaches. Significant challenges remain, however, in the use of commercial FE codes, regarding element selection and representation of the laminate. Impact damage modeling has been applied in the research domain for quite some time with recent successful results

[5-9]. With the recent implementation of cohesive zone based fracture prediction into commercial software (e.g., ABAQUS, LS-Dyna), representation of delamination failure modes is now more accessible to a wider range of analysts. The focus of this paper is the definition of a methodology for using commercial FE software to accurately simulate blunt impact damage on large-sized composite structures, capturing key local failure modes and processes, while also matching overall global-level structural response.

High energy wide area blunt impacts of fuselage structures by GSE were investigated [4] using large-sized 1.8x2 m composite panel specimens, designed to be representative of current commercial aircraft fuselage designs (see large panel specimen identified as “Frame03” in Figure 1). The panel specimens consisted of carbon fiber skin, co-cured hat stringers, shear ties, and five frames (full details are in references [4] and [10]). During impact, the shear ties sustained delamination and fiber fracture damage (see Figure 1) that led to extensive frame rotation, followed by global structural deformations and ultimately frame failures.

Figure 1. Five-frame panel specimen description (top), specimen Frame03 blunt impact setup showing 1 m rubber bumper loading (left), and interior view of damage to shear ties during impact (right).

In order to understand the process of failure initiation and stiffness loss, an inverted building-block pyramid approach was taken where failure modes that were observed during the large-scale specimen tests were used to guide the focused study of these failure modes using small-scale "element-level" tests. Isolated experiments were conducted on small-sized shear tie element-level specimens (see Figure 2) to support the development of accurate FE analysis models. The shear tie coupons were constrained with boundary conditions similar to those in the fuselage panel, and compressed to represent deformation modes induced by GSE impact loading (see Figure 1). FE simulation of the small-scale tests required employment of cohesive zone modeling and intra-ply failure criteria which were implemented to capture the delamination and fiber fracture damage. Upon establishing validation of these failure mode predictions at the small-scale level, modeling definitions were then transferred to the large-scale fuselage model. The end result was a fuselage model capable of predicting the small scale damage formation in the shear ties, their effect on subsequent panel deformations, and global stiffness degradation observed in the full-scale experiments.

Figure 2. Shear tie element specimen geometry (left) and compression experimental setup (right).

2 SHEAR TIE ELEMENT-LEVEL EXPERIMENTS

To support the development of accurate FE modeling, small-sized shear tie coupons were fabricated and subjected to direct compression loading (see Figure 2). These coupon compression experiments represent the shear ties under direct blunt impact loading, as seen in the large 5-frame specimens (see Figure 1). Compression load from the impact caused the shear ties to delaminate, crush, and fracture in buckling. Once fractured, the shear ties completely lost their load bearing capability. The C-frames were then allowed to twist, leading to wide-spread failure of additional surrounding shear ties and eventually of the frame members. These experiments are described in detail in references [4] and [10]. To accurately model the blunt impact damage, it was desirable to understand these failure modes and accurately model the initial damage and subsequent progression.

The shear tie compression coupons were 66 mm wide sections, cut from the same shear ties used in the large 5-frame panel impact experiment. Figure 2 shows the element-level specimen geometry and the test setup. The shear tie coupon was bolted to a curved aluminum support plate, similar to the shear tie to skin connection of the large specimens. An aluminum V-notched plate was used to apply compression loading on the top of the shear tie flange via contact (see Figure 2), with the V-shaped slot providing a pivoting boundary condition. This upper boundary condition is a simplified representation of the connection of the shear ties to the large panel's C-frames. The entire setup was mounted into a uniaxial testing machine to apply compression loading under displacement-control.

The in-plane compression applied to the vertical flange produced bending and shearing stresses at the curved corner of the shear tie. A simplified free body diagram of the shear tie corner is shown in Figure 3. The shear tie corner can be considered as a 90° sweep curved beam section with a constant radius R , fixed on one side with in-plane loading applied to the other side, as shown. While the shear force remains uniform throughout the length of the curved beam, when resolved in the through-thickness direction, the highest transverse shear stress occurred at the fixed base (point B in Figure 3) at the same location as maximum bending moment. Opening moment produces radial tension stress [11] and combined with the through-thickness transverse shear stress, both contribute to the formation of delamination damage via Mode I and II loading, respectively. Therefore, it is expected that the delamination would initiate at this location.

Figure 3. (a) Simplified free-body diagram of the shear tie corner, (b) the corresponding shear force and moment diagram on the shear tie corner.

The shear tie element compression experiments were conducted quasi-statically at 6 mm/min. Figures 4 shows a series of photographs taken during the compression test and Figure 5 the shows force vs. actuator displacement plot of a typical test. The events corresponding to each photograph in Figure 4 are indicted in Figure 5. Figure 4a shows the pristine coupon before loading. At 2 mm of crosshead displacement and 7.0 kN load, delamination damage occurred at one of the interface layers, and caused the first load drop (see curved region in Figure4b and point b in Figure 5). The delamination damage appeared to have extended across the width of the coupon because the crack was visible on both sides. As the delamination caused the shear tie corner to soften, additional compression loading produced more opening of the shear tie corner, and additional delaminations at the other interface layers. The cumulative delamination damage corresponded to the decreasing stiffness of the loading curve between 2 and 5 mm of cross head displacement, until the corner region was flattened against the aluminum support plate.

At 4.9 mm of compressive displacement, the shear tie corner had fully flattened as shown in Figure 4c. However, the flange remained in a vertical position, causing a kink in the laminate between the flange and corner of the shear tie. Figure4c shows the outer ply failures caused by the kink. This ply failure was driven by the highly localized transverse shear and bending stresses at the kink. Since the vertical flange made contact with the base plate, the softened shear tie corner was no longer in the load path. The compression load was now directly carried by the shear tie flange (like a vertical plate in compression). Hence, the stiffness of the coupon increased for increasing crosshead displacement beyond 5 mm. Additional compression caused bending and lateral deflection of the shear tie flange. This second deformation mode occurred until buckling failure of the flange occurred at 13.9 mm of displacement and 10.4 kN of load (see Figure4d).

3 MODEL DEVELOPMENT

The shear tie compression coupon, modeled using Abaqus, was developed with its plies separated into ply groups, as shown in Figure 6, to allow for delamination modeling via the cohesive zone approach. The shear tie layup consisted of 12 plies of 6K plain weave carbon/epoxy X840 Z60 fabric provided by Cytec Engineered Materials; layup was $[(45/0)_3]_S$. Geometry of the model was identical to the test specimen. The model was constrained to a fixed aluminum support plate via surface tie constraint. A pivoting displacement constraint was applied to the top of the shear tie flange, in lieu of modeling the V-notched loading plate. In the model, contact between the shear tie corner elements and the aluminum support plate were accounted for by using a frictionless penalty contact interaction between these two surfaces. Due to the compressive loading and crushing failure mode at the shear tie corner, element instability was an ongoing issue. This was especially true for the shear tie model that would be implemented into the large-size Frame03 fuselage panel impact simulation, due to the increase in the number of shear ties.

Figure 4. (a) Pristine shear tie compression specimen, (b) initial delamination at shear tie corner, (c) crushing failure and flattening of the corner, (d) buckling failure of the flange.

Figure 5. Force vs. crosshead displacement plot of a shear tie compression coupon.

Figure 6. Shear tie layup, ply grouping, and cohesive zone layers configuration.

The shear tie model was multi-layered in order to capture the bending response, transverse shear stresses, and the complex, mixed failure modes that occurred at different locations. Fiber fracture damage at the shear tie corners occurred due to transverse shear and bending stresses. The Hill failure criterion for orthotropic materials was used to model the shear ties corner failures to achieve the desired 3D stress failure modes. The Hill criterion failure envelope was defined as:

$$I_F = \frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{X^2} + \frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{Y^2} + \frac{\sigma_{33}^2}{Z^2} - \frac{\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22}}{X^2} - \frac{\sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{Y^2} - \frac{\sigma_{11}\sigma_{33}}{Z^2} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{S_{12}^2} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{S_{23}^2} + \frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{S_{13}^2} = 1 \quad (1)$$

Failure initiation was triggered when a stress component exceeded the material's strength. The variables X , Y , Z , S_{12} , S_{23} , and S_{13} were material strengths defined in Table 1, where the primed values indicate compression values. This failure criterion was similar to the Hill-Tsai criterion, with the exception that compressive and tensile material strengths are not distinct. For example, X represented both the compressive and tensile stress limit in the 1-1 direction. However, this was acceptable for modeling the X840 Z60 plain wave carbon fiber fabric because there was no strong difference between its in-plane compressive and tensile strengths. Also, due to the lack of published data and generally accepted methods of determining the intra-laminar (i.e., transverse failure of fibers within a ply) transverse shear strengths of the fabric material, these values were approximated as two times the interlaminar strength of the laminated composite.

Table 1. Material properties

Elastic Properties	ρ (g/cm ³)	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	
Fabric	1.61	80	80	0.06	6.48	5.1	4.07	
Strength Properties	X (MPa)	X' (MPa)	Y (MPa)	Y' (MPa)	Z (MPa)	S_{12} (MPa)	S_{23} (MPa)	S_{13} (MPa)
Fabric	993	772	855	896	45.9	71	77.9	77.9
Interlaminar Fracture	G_{nc} (J/m ²)	G_{sc} (J/m ²)	G_{tc} (J/m ²)					
Fabric	771	3152	3152					

The quasi-brittle failure behavior of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy was modeled by using a modified damage law for ductile damage. By setting the equivalent plastic strain at failure to zero, the plasticity zone was removed and the material transitioned into the damage regime once its elastic limits were reached. Figure 7 shows the stress-strain curve describing the intra-ply failures. At the onset of failure, equivalent strain was used in this damage law to govern the overall failure parameter. A single fracture energy value was assigned for the combined intra-ply damage modes. Since ply fracture occurred via bending (in-plane tension and compression stresses) and out-of-plane shearing of fibers, the fracture energy was approximated as 45.8 KJ/m² based on the fracture energy of the T300-913 carbon fiber fabric reinforced toughened epoxy [12].

Figure 7. Modified stress-strain relationship governing damage degradation relationship.

12 layers of solid elements (C3D8R) were used to model the shear tie element compression specimens. Each ply was represented with one layer of elements stacked in the thickness direction (see Figures 6 and 8). An element was deleted when it sustained damage, and its load bearing capability was reduced by 95%. The solid element was found to be more suitable for simulating crushing damage since this element had comprehensive element distortion and enhanced hourglass controls to prevent numerical instability issues. Specifically, element distortion control prevented nodal movement past the center of the element, and enhanced hourglass control prevented zero energy displacement modes caused by reduce integration of the element. Both the distortion control and enhanced hourglass control increased the element's stability by adding penalty stiffness to the element.

Figure 8 shows the final mesh and a series of deformation images for the twelve layer solid element shear tie FE model. The simulation's force vs. applied displacement results have been plotted in Figure 9 along with the experimental data for three separate tests. The 12 layer shear tie model correctly predicted the initial delamination load, as well as the shear tie crushing behavior up to 11 mm of crosshead displacement. However, the buckling failure along the shear tie flange was not captured, perhaps because of over-stiffening from the numerical controls. Finally, the shear tie model severed at the shear tie corner as shown in Figure 9d. After the ply element failure initiated, the contact force oscillated due to the high contact stresses experienced by the elements located at the shear tie corner. The ply failure criteria were triggered at the shear tie corner, and elements were degraded and removed from the simulation.

Figure 8. (a) Unloaded shear tie compression model with 12 layers of solid elements through the thickness, (b) close up view of the initial delamination at shear tie corner, (c) flattening of the shear tie corner, and (d) crushing failure and severing at the shear tie corner.

Figure 9. Load vs. displacement plot of the shear tie compression experiments and FE model results.

4 MODEL APPLICATION TO LARGE-SCALE STRUCTURE SIMULATION

Modeling definitions from the shear tie experiment were transferred to models of the large-scale experiments. The panel behavior before and after shear tie failures was accurately captured with the solid element shear tie model. Figure 10 shows the load vs. indentation plot of the Frame03 test compared with the updated FE model results. Figures 11 and 12 show the key panel failures at various time during impact from the experiments and modeling results, respectively.

In the updated FE model, the impacted shear ties behaved similarly as shown in Figure 8. Delamination of the impacted shear ties occurred at 65 kN (see point a in Figure 10). Then, crushing of the impacted shear ties at the curved corners initiated at 79.5 kN (see point b) to cause an initial load drop, which occurred at a much higher load than in the experiment. Between 18.6 and 28.0 mm of displacement, the shear tie corner crushing failure occurred (between points b and c), producing some oscillations in the contact force. After the shear tie corners were crushed, the shear tie flange acted as a flat plate in direct compression (much like in Figure 8c), thus allowing the load to quickly build up. At point c in Figure 10, the center shear tie flange fractured either at the corner or at halfway between the corner and bolt line. Figure 11a and 12a show model and experimental shear tie fracture failure in the impact zone. The load path was then redirected to the shear ties adjacent to the impact zone, as well as via direct contact between the stringer and C-frame, as shown in Figure 11b and 12b. C-frame twisting was driven by the contact force being applied offset from the C-shape section's shear center, so large C-frame rotation caused the shear ties adjacent to the impact zone to fail in bending. Figures 11c and 12c show the shear ties adjacent to the impact zone undergoing fracture with large C-frame rotation, corresponding to point d in Figure 10. This model was accurate for up to 70 mm of indentation, at which time the C-frames were predicted by the model to fail near the outer boundary conditions, whereas in the actual test, frame failure did not occur until 85 mm of indentation.

Figure 10. Contact force vs. indentation plot of the Frame03 test and FE model with solid element shear ties.

Figure 11. Frame03 half model: (a) impacted shear tie corner fracture damage, (b) C-frame contact with stringer and twisting, and (c) fracture of adjacent set of shear ties with frame failure.

Figure 12. Frame03 experiment (compare right-half with Figure 11 images): (a) impacted shear tie corner fracture damage, (b) C-frame twisting, and (c) adjacent shear tie bending failure at the bolt line.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Analysis and simulation of a large-scale panel was broken down into simpler, small-size parts, and a key failure mode was examined via small-sized setup that replicated those failure modes observed in the large-scale tests. A simpler structural element test was conducted, with loading and boundary conditions for the small-scale experiments defined in a manner that replicated conditions of the

structural element as it exists within the large-scale specimen. The simple small-sized specimen experiments supported development of a FE modeling methodology that accurately captures the key physics and failure modes, based on best-known material properties inputs. The simple geometry and boundary conditions of the element-level specimens helped to increase the efficiency of the model development due to shorter modeling run time thereby allowing many modeling iterations. The resulting models showed very good correlation at the element-level. The modeling definitions were next transferred to the large-scale panel models and shown to accurately capture the large-sized panel response, including key failure modes and loads at which those failures occurred.

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